

Greenhouse Gas Emissions, Carbon Sequestration in Cropland and Crop Yield Limiting Factors

Ali DEVLET ^{1*}

¹ Bilecik Seyh Edebali University, Faculty of Agriculture and Natural Science, Department of Field Crops, Bilecik

*Corresponding author: ali.devlet@bilecik.edu.tr

Received: 10.07.2024

Accepted: 30.08.2024

Abstract

Global warming has seriously affected human survival and sustainable development of agriculture. The direct cause of global warming is likely to be the excessive emission of greenhouse gases. Greenhouse gases mainly include carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O), ozone (O₃) and water vapor. Due to the rapid change of global climate, the situation has further deteriorated. In crop production, drought is undoubtedly the most important stress which has a great impact on crop growth and productivity. Understanding the physiological, biochemical and ecological interventions associated with these stresses is important for better management. Abiotic stress is one of the main constraints of crop production and food security in the world. This review explores the scientific foundations of greenhouse gas emissions and carbon sequestration in agricultural lands. It examines the negative impacts of drought stress on plant responses, crop growth, and yield formation. Additionally, it assesses the gap between actual yields and potential yields, highlighting the limiting factors that have not been adequately addressed. This issue is prevalent in agricultural production across all countries.

Keywords: Greenhouse gas emissions, carbon sequestration, abiotic stress, yield limiting factors

1. Introduction

In recent years, the relationship between greenhouse gas emissions, carbon sequestration in farmland, and crop yield limiting factors has received widespread attention, especially in the context of global food security increasingly threatened by climate change. Agricultural practices have made significant contributions to greenhouse gas emissions through soil disturbance and fertilization (Smith et al., 2021). On the contrary, farmland may serve as a carbon sink through practices such as cover planting, no till agriculture, and agricultural ecological methods (Johnson et al., 2022). Recent studies have shown that strengthening carbon sequestration can not only alleviate climate change, but also improve soil health and crop resilience (Zhang and Liu, 2023). However, challenges such as soil degradation, water scarcity, and nutrient deficiencies continue to limit crop yields, making it necessary to comprehensively understand these dynamics (Thompson et al., 2024).

Seeds are essential entities that store plant genetic information vital for adaptation throughout the plant life cycle. As critical reproductive units, seeds significantly impact crop production and human survival. Quality seeds ensure high yields across various crop types and growing conditions (Bradford and Bewley, 2002). They offer superior genetic purity and characteristics such as high germination rates, uniform growth patterns, and resistance to diseases and pests (Basra, 1995). Seed quality is influenced by genetic factors, including the mother plant's composition, age, and nutritional status, as well as physical factors like temperature, water conditions, and soil nutrients (Bradford and Bewley, 2002; Finch-Savage and Leubner Metzger, 2006; Nambara and Nonogogaki, 2012). The use of high-quality seeds maximizes crop genetic potential and provides high returns per area, with benefits including adaptability to extreme conditions and ease

of harvesting (Bradford and Bewley, 2002; Nambara and Nonogogaki, 2012). Despite their importance, many farmers, especially in developing countries, struggle to access high-quality seeds due to inadequate production and distribution systems. The FAO has established guidelines to ensure seed quality from production to delivery (FAO, 2014). Efforts to improve seed quality through breeding and biotechnology have been significant, with seed companies focusing on traits like insect resistance and water-use efficiency to enhance crop yields (Rinukshi, 2015).

Global food consumption heavily relies on wheat, rice, corn, barley, and sorghum, all of which are vulnerable to climate change, particularly global warming and prolonged drought. In Asia and Africa, rain-fed agriculture is expected to suffer significantly, with potential losses of about 280 million tons of grain production (Singh et al., 2013). Rising temperatures can decrease seed numbers and sizes and alter physiological conditions in many plant species (Martínez et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2013). Predictions indicate that rice and corn production in South Asia may drop by 10% by 2030, with southern Africa facing a 30% reduction (Lobell et al., 2008). The International Rice Institute has found that temperatures above 35°C during flowering can cause sterility, leading to a 20% reduction in rice production (IRRI, 2014).

Greenhouse gases (GHGs) significantly influence climate by absorbing and releasing energy. While carbon dioxide is the primary contributor to global warming, other gases like methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) also play critical roles (Denman et al., 2007; Velders et al., 2010). Without global efforts to reduce these emissions, they will continue to rise, exacerbating climate change (Fisher et al., 2007; Townsend et al., 2010). Understanding the emissions from human activities and natural processes is essential for effective mitigation strategies (Montzka et al., 2011). Rapid population

growth, fluctuating climate conditions, and food insecurity are pressing issues today (Hussain and Sulaimon, 2018). High temperatures and drought are major constraints on crop production, contributing to a global drought-like situation (Rajsekhar and Gorelick, 2017). Extreme drought has led to significant yield declines in crops like wheat and maize, with observed reductions of 21% and 40%, respectively (Daryanto et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2018). Over the past 30 years, the global average temperature has

risen by 0.85 °C, with projections of an additional 0.2°C increase every decade (Friedlingstein et al., 2010). Each temperature rise could decrease global wheat yields by about 6% (Asseng et al., 2015). While some regions may benefit from warmer temperatures, the overall impact on global food security remains concerning (Challinor et al., 2014). Insufficient water supply exacerbates drought conditions, affecting plant health and yield (Lisar et al., 2012). The detailed system representation is shown in Figure 1.

Figure. 1 A stress state in which plant yield decreases due to drought (Iqbal et al., 2020)

Drought damage is unpredictable, influenced by factors like rainfall patterns, soil water retention, and high transpiration rates (Yan et al., 2016). Drought affects plant growth by disrupting photosynthesis and nutrient uptake, leading to significant declines in crop productivity (Praba et al., 2009; Muhammad et al., 2012). Plant responses to drought vary by species and growth stage (Cheruth et al., 2009). Insufficient soil moisture limits photosynthetic radiation absorption and reduces harvest indices, contributing to yield declines (Earl and Davis, 2003).

Severe drought alters growth patterns and physiological processes (Duan et al., 2007). Heat stress also hampers plant development (Akter and Islam, 2017; Jalil and Ansari, 2018). Global warming-induced drought is increasingly limiting crop yield and productivity, emphasizing the need for effective crop management strategies. Human diets heavily rely on wheat (*Triticum aestivum L.*), maize (*Zea mays L.*), and rice (*Oryza sativa L.*), whose production has surged over the past 50 years due to land management improvements and new technologies

(Cassman, 1999; FAO, 2002a). Future agricultural demand is expected to rise, but land expansion is limited (Rosegrant, 2003). Agricultural intensification is essential for enhancing crop production (Ruttan, 2002; Barbier, 2003). However, food production growth has stagnated in many regions (Cassman, 1999; Rosegrant, 2003; Trostle, 2008). The yield gap, the difference between actual and potential crop yields, is poorly understood globally. This gap arises from inconsistent data on agricultural intensification drivers and limited land management information (Keys and McConnell, 2005). Many studies highlight local factors affecting food production, making it challenging to identify universal drivers (Timsina and Connor, 2001; FAO, 2002a; Reidsma et al., 2007). Furthermore, yield gap analyses often rely on crop models that simulate potential yields without accounting for local variations (Rockström and Falkenmark, 2000; Van Ittersum et al., 2013). While satellite data can enhance understanding of crop yield gaps, integrating this information with local data remains a significant challenge (Lobell, 2013).

2. Greenhouse gas emission and carbon sequestration in cropland

In the pre-industrial era, a natural balance existed between carbon dioxide emissions from sources (fossil fuels) and sinks (forests and oceans). However, since the industrial period, emissions have risen due to insufficient regulations, while deforestation and industrial expansion have reduced carbon sinks, particularly forest cover. Maintaining forest cover at 33% of land area is crucial for balancing land degradation and enhancing carbon absorption. There is a negative correlation between forest coverage and both population density and atmospheric CO₂ levels. Countries share the atmosphere as a common resource, necessitating international cooperation on greenhouse gas emissions through frameworks like the

Paris Agreement (UNFCCC, 2015) and Intended Nationally Determined Contributions (INDCs) (Venkatramanan et al., 2020b). Recent years have seen a rise in global average temperatures, driven by greenhouse gases (GHGs) like CO₂, methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O) (IPCC, 2014). CH₄ is particularly concerning, with a Global Warming Potential (GWP) significantly higher than CO₂ over various timeframes. Agricultural practices are major sources of GHGs, with farmland contributing approximately 12.5% of CO₂, 50% of CH₄, and 60% of N₂O emissions globally. For instance, paddy fields account for about 20% of global CH₄ emissions (IPCC, 2007). Soil organic carbon (SOC) plays a dual role as both a carbon source and sink. Practices like conservation tillage can enhance SOC accumulation, improving soil health and productivity (Lal et al., 2004). However, land-use changes, such as converting grasslands and forests to farmland, can release significant amounts of SOC into the atmosphere. Methane emissions from agricultural systems, particularly rice paddies, are substantial, with China contributing approximately 500 million tons annually. Strategies like alternating wet and dry irrigation have successfully reduced CH₄ emissions in China. However, understanding the mechanisms of GHG emissions in diverse agricultural systems remains insufficient, particularly regarding the interplay between N₂O and CH₄ emissions (Qiu et al., 2009). Future research should focus on regional monitoring and understanding the dynamics of GHG emissions in various cropping systems, particularly rice fields. Establishing sustainable agricultural practices that enhance carbon sequestration while maintaining productivity is essential for addressing climate change (Tan and Zhang, 2009). Strengthening the incentive mechanisms for soil carbon sequestration and enhancing research on SOC dynamics in farmland, especially in paddy systems, will provide valuable insights for policy-

making and agricultural practices (Pan et al., 2005). The impacts of climate change on ecosystems and human health underscore the importance of effective mitigation strategies. In Figure 2, we

summarize the impact pathways from carbon dioxide emissions to damage to ecosystems and human health covered by IPCC Fifth Assessment Report (AR5) (IPCC, 2014).

Figure 2. Damage pathways of greenhouse gas emissions to different protection areas, adapted from (IPCC, 2014a; Yan Dong et al., 2019)

Human health damage accounts for 70-97% of the monetary value of greenhouse gases, with CO₂ equivalent valued at approximately \$16, \$160, and \$140 per ton (Yan Dong et al., 2019). The uncertainty in these values can be significant, often by 1-2 orders of magnitude. Climate change, driven by anthropogenic greenhouse gases, is expected to increase flood frequency and severity, leading to estimated damages of \$300 billion over 100 years for major port cities (Hanson et al., 2011). Annual global flood-related losses are projected to rise from \$6 billion to \$100 billion by 2100 (Hallegatte et al., 2013). The socio-economic impacts of climate change could lead to conflicts over land and resources, reminiscent of the Second World War, which caused direct economic losses of \$11 trillion and 77 million deaths (Thompson, 2014). If climate change triggers similar conflicts, the estimated cost could be \$61 per ton of CO₂ equivalent. To manage greenhouse gas

emissions effectively, eco-intensive crop management practices are essential (Cassman, 1999). High-yield crops, when grown with best management practices (BMPs), can enhance soil carbon storage while minimizing greenhouse gas emissions. For example, in Nebraska, strategies such as selecting adaptive varieties, optimizing water and nitrogen management, and returning crop residues to the soil can reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Dobermann et al., 2007). The three primary agricultural greenhouse gases—CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O—differ in their global warming potential (GWP). Over 100 years, CH₄ has a GWP of 23 and N₂O has a GWP of 296 compared to CO₂ (IPCC, 2001). While CO₂ is heavily utilized in photosynthesis, methane is primarily emitted from rice cultivation and livestock, and nitrous oxide is produced during nitrification and denitrification processes in soil (Bange, 2000; Snyder et al., 2009). Optimizing nitrogen fertilizer

use can stabilize plant productivity and soil carbon storage while minimizing emissions. Current estimates suggest that 1% of nitrogen application results in N₂O emissions (IPCC, 2006), with variations based on local conditions. Reducing emissions of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases can significantly mitigate climate forcing and improve air and water quality (Fisher et al., 2007; Van Vuuren et al., 2006). Scientific advancements are crucial for understanding greenhouse gas flux sensitivities and improving emission quantification. The Montreal Protocol serves as a successful model for controlling atmospheric pollutants, demonstrating the potential for effective emission management to stabilize climate forcing (Montzka et al., 1999; Miller et al., 2010). In summary, managing both CO₂ and non-CO₂ greenhouse gas emissions is vital for climate stability, requiring a focus on eco-intensive practices, improved scientific understanding, and effective policy measures.

3. Crop production under drought condition

Drought conditions, characterized by limited root water supply and high transpiration loss, significantly impact plant growth and yield (Anjum et al., 2011). The severity of drought damage is unpredictable, influenced by rainfall patterns, soil water capacity, and evapotranspiration (Farooq et al., 2009; Praba et al., 2009). Drought affects growth, nutrient-water relationships, photosynthesis, and assimilate allocation, leading to reduced crop yields (Demirevska et al., 2009). Key factors contributing to yield reduction include decreased absorption of photosynthetically active radiation, diminished radiation use efficiency, and lower harvest indices (Earl and Davis, 2003). Initial drought effects manifest as poor germination and seedling development, impacting crops such as *Pisum sativum*, *Medicago sativa*, and *Oryza sativa* (Okcu et al., 2005; Manikavelu et al., 2006; Zeid and Sheeded,

2006). Drought restricts cell division and elongation, leading to reduced leaf number and size (Hussain et al., 2008; Taiz and Zeiger, 2006). For instance, maize exhibits significant decreases in height, leaf size, and biomass under drought (Khan et al., 2015; Kamara et al., 2003). Drought stress primarily reduces germination rates and seedling formation (Li et al., 2011). Studies indicate that drought negatively impacts seed germination and early growth (Kaya et al., 2006; Hatzig et al., 2018). The physiological processes essential for growth, such as cell elongation and mitosis, are compromised, leading to reduced plant growth (Farooq et al., 2009). Furthermore, drought stress reduces leaf area and expansion pressure, further limiting photosynthesis and growth (Rucker et al., 1995; Zhao et al., 2006). Yield is influenced by multiple physiological processes, all adversely affected by drought stress (Ali et al., 2017). The timing of drought exposure is critical; pre-anthesis drought can shorten flowering time, while post-anthesis drought affects grain filling (Farooq et al., 2009). Key enzymes involved in grain filling, such as Adenosine Diphosphate (ADP) glucose pyrophosphorylase, starch branching enzyme, and sucrose Uridine Diphosphate (UDP) glucosyltransferase, show decreased activity under drought (Ainsworth et al., 1995; Ahmadi and Baker, 2001). Stomatal closure is a primary response to water stress, limiting CO₂ intake and leading to oxidative damage (Ludlow and Muchow, 1990; Yokota et al., 2002). This response is influenced more by soil water status than leaf moisture (Turner et al., 2001). Drought also impairs photosynthesis by reducing stomatal conductance and damaging Rubisco function (Bota et al., 2004). The synthesis of key photosynthetic enzymes is negatively impacted by drought, leading to reduced Adenosine Triphosphate (ATP) production and impaired photosynthetic efficiency (Lawlor and Cornic, 2002). Overall, drought stress leads to reduced

leaf area, impaired photosynthetic mechanisms, and altered photosynthetic pigments, significantly affecting plant growth and yield (Fu and Huang, 2001; Monakhova and Chernyadev, 2002; Wahid and Rasul, 2005). Research highlights the critical need for understanding and

mitigating the impacts of drought on agriculture to improve crop resilience and yield stability under changing climatic conditions. The effect of drought stress on photosynthesis mechanism is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Drought Stress Affects Photosynthesis and leads to growth and development (Iqbal et al., 2020)

Water scarcity leads to cell shrinkage and reduced cell volume, causing substances within cells to become more viscous and resulting in protein denaturation (Ghosh and Dill, 2010). High solute concentrations in the cytoplasm can induce ionic toxicity, severely affecting enzymes essential for photosynthesis (Hussain et al., 2018). The presence of Rubisco in plant leaves is contingent on its production and degradation, remaining relatively stable even under severe water shortages due to its short half-life (Quick et al., 1991; Hoekstra et al., 2001). However, reduced production of Rubisco due to the contraction of its secondary subunit is a significant loss (Vu et al., 1999). Other

crucial photosynthetic enzymes are also adversely affected by drought (Farooq et al., 2012), with decreased phosphorylation and ATP synthesis being key factors limiting photosynthesis (Lawler and Cornic, 2002). Water relations in plants are influenced by factors such as leaf water potential, canopy and leaf temperature, transpiration rate, and stomatal conductance (Waring and Landsberg, 2011). Drought stress particularly impacts stomatal conductance, leading to decreased transpiration rates and increased leaf temperatures (Turner et al., 2001). Water use efficiency (WUE), defined as the ratio of accumulated dry matter to water consumed, is crucial for plant survival

under drought (Monclus et al., 2006). Some wheat varieties exhibit high WUE due to effective stomatal closure and reduced transpiration rates (Abbate et al., 2004). Early water shortages in *Solanum* plants can lead to decreased biomass and yield (Obidiegwu et al., 2015). Drought significantly affects the nutrient composition of plants, disrupting the absorption of essential nutrients like nitrogen, magnesium, calcium, and silicon (Barber, 1995). Root structure changes, including increased length and surface area, help plants adapt to acquire less mobile nutrients (Lynch and Brown, 2001). However, soil water deficits can hinder root growth and nutrient absorption (Garg, 2003). The interaction between roots and microorganisms is vital for nutrient uptake, and drought stress can impair nitrogen fixation in legumes (Ladrera et al., 2007; Schimel et al., 2007). Different crops respond variably to mineral absorption under drought, with nitrogen absorption typically increasing while phosphorus absorption decreases. Abiotic stress,

particularly drought and high temperatures, poses significant threats to crop production and food security, exacerbated by climate change. Understanding the physiological, biochemical, and ecological responses of plants to these stresses is essential for effective management strategies. Plant responses include morphological, physiological, and biochemical adaptations, with reproductive stages being particularly vulnerable (Fahad et al., 2017). Recent advancements in genetic methods and stress resistance techniques have shown promise, but challenges remain regarding the interaction between genetics and environmental factors. To enhance yield stability under drought, an integrated systems approach combining genomics, quantitative genetics, and ecophysiology is essential (Hawkesford and Buchner, 2001; Araus et al., 2003; Alaus, 2004). Most current research lacks this interdisciplinary framework, highlighting the need for comprehensive studies to improve crop resilience against abiotic stresses.

Figure 4. The response of plants to drought stress is complex, which is determined by genetic and environmental factors. The optimization of field water use needs an integrated system approach that takes into account crop management, environmental and genetic factors. Recombined inbred lines (Parry et al., 2005).

4. Crop yield and limiting factors

Recent concerns about meeting projected food demand through increased crop productivity have highlighted that "business as usual" will not suffice, potentially leading to rising food prices, poverty, and hunger (FAO, 2003; FAO, 2006; Royal Society of London, 2009; Koning and Van Gitson, 2009). Traditional computational models predicted stable or declining food prices, but significant changes in global food security predictions have emerged due to: (1) faster-than-expected economic development in populous countries, (2) increased demand for food and livestock products driven by rising purchasing power, and (3) a global slowdown in grain yield rates (Cassman et al., 2003; Royal Society of London, 2009; Cassman et al., 2010; Brisson et al., 2010; Fischer and Edmeades, 2010). As the global population approaches nine billion, existing crop land must yield significantly more. Some regions have higher potential for sustainable production due to better climate and soil quality, yet current yields in these areas are low, indicating a large yield gap. Identifying regions with the greatest potential for increased food supply is crucial for several reasons: it helps prioritize crops, guides research and interventions, assesses climate change impacts, and informs economic models for food security (Martin et al., 2013). Historical examples demonstrate the effectiveness of yield gap analysis. For

instance, wheat yields in the Netherlands have exceeded expectations, and improved management practices in Australia have reduced yield gaps (French and Schultz, 1984; Hochman et al., 2012). In Southeast Asia, nitrogen management improvements are needed for irrigated rice yields (Kropff et al., 1993), while a yield gap analysis in Nebraska revealed stagnation in maize yields (Grassini et al., 2011). Research on yield gaps has utilized various methods, including crop growth models and remote sensing technologies, revealing that biological, environmental, technical, economic, and policy factors contribute to yield differences (Wang et al., 2009). Improving crop yield focuses on enhancing yield potential (Y_p) and narrowing the yield gap (Wang, 2004). Y_p represents the maximum yield under optimal conditions, while water-limited yield (Y_w) accounts for water supply constraints. Average yield (Y_a) reflects the actual yield obtained by farmers under typical management practices (Evans, 1993; Van Ittersum and Rabbinge, 1997). Yield levels can be categorized into four tiers: theoretical yield based on light and temperature, high-yield records, regional test yields, and average field yields. The differences between these levels constitute the yield gap, with various factors identified as yield constraints (Martin et al., 2013). Therefore, the difference of crop yield can be defined as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Definition of crop yield potential and yield difference (Li, 2011)

The theoretical yield of light and temperature represents the highest potential yield based on regional light and temperature resources, while the high yield record reflects the maximum yield achieved in the region. The regional test yield indicates the results from experimental fields, and the average yield per unit area denotes the actual yield obtained by local farmers. Yield differences are categorized as follows: Yield Difference I is the gap between regional test yield and average field yield; Yield Difference II is the gap between the high yield record and regional test yield; Yield Difference III is the gap between theoretical yield and the high yield record. For example, in China, maize's theoretical yield ranges from 27,349.5 to 47,490.0 kg/ha, whereas average yields are only 3,836.3 to 7,271.0 kg/ha, representing just 14.7% of the theoretical yield (Li, 2011). Since the mid-1970s, various conceptual models have emerged to explore the causes of yield gaps. Gomez identified two types of gaps: Gap I, which is due to environmental differences between

experimental stations and farmers' fields, and Gap II, which arises from biological, technological, and socio-economic constraints (Gomez, 1977). Lin Yifu highlighted two yield gaps in China's rice production: one between maximum experimental yields and farmers' potential yields, and another between farmers' potential and actual yields, with the latter influenced by environmental and management factors. The FAO's comparative performance analysis indicated that water shortage, diseases, and sowing dates are significant contributors to yield gaps (FAO). To address these gaps, researchers have emphasized the need for high-yield crop establishment and narrowing the yield gap between regional test yields and farmers' actual yields (Li, 2011). While achieving high yields is important, understanding the limiting factors of crop yield and resource constraints is essential for sustainable agricultural development (Evenson et al., 1997; Duvick and Cassman, 1999). Challenges in understanding yield differences include the complexity of

agroecosystems, lack of spatial data on crop yields, and farmers' focus on economic benefits. The yield gap (Y_g) is defined as the difference between potential yield (Y_p for irrigated crops or Y_w for dry crops) and actual yield (Y_a). Water productivity, or the efficiency of water use in food production, is increasingly important due to pressure on water resources (Bessembinder et al., 2005;

Passioura, 2006; Grassini et al., 2011). Achieving Y_p or Y_w is often impractical for many farmers due to cost-effectiveness and diminishing returns on inputs (Koning et al., 2008; Lobell et al., 2009). Future research must focus on narrowing the yield gap while balancing resource efficiency and economic viability (De Wit, 1992). The schematic diagram of these key parameters is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Different levels of production determined by growth definition, limiting and reducing factors (a). The yield potential (Y_p) of crops under non water limited irrigation depends on solar radiation (R), temperature condition (T) and growth period from planting to maturity. For crops grown under dry farming conditions, water limited yield (Y_w) represents the highest yield (Van itersum and Rabbinge, 1997). The recoverable production gap (b) represents the difference between the average production and 80% of Y_p or Y_w , as described in the paper (modified from Lobell et al., 2009; Martin et al., 2013).

Yield potential (Y_p), water-limited yield (Y_w), actual yield (Y_a), and yield gap (Y_g) are estimated based on geographical units and time frames. By applying appropriate amplification programs, it is possible to quantify individual farm yields over time and space (Ewert et al., 2011). Climate change can alter these yield levels by impacting temperature and water availability, farmers' adaptation strategies, and the prevalence of diseases and pests. This manuscript emphasizes quantifying current yield values for two main reasons: to identify causes of yield limitations and to assess the impact of climate change on future yields and food security (Martin et al., 2013). A review of organic versus conventional yield data was conducted using various literature databases, focusing on yield comparisons in organic and traditional agriculture. The search aimed to encompass diverse terminologies associated with organic farming, adhering to the International Federation of Organic Agriculture Movements (IFOAM) standards, which exclude artificial fertilizers and promote biodiversity and soil fertility (Tomek et al., 2012). Discussions on crop yield gaps typically focus on two objectives: measuring the yield gap (the difference between Y_p and average yield) and identifying the main causes of this gap to enhance productivity through targeted management changes (Van Ittersum et al., 2013; Martin et al., 2013). However, spatial and temporal heterogeneity in agricultural landscapes poses challenges. Yield estimates often vary across different administrative units, complicating comparisons between localized agronomic experiments and broader regional data (Lobell et al., 2009). To address these challenges, remote sensing technologies have emerged as valuable tools for assessing agricultural heterogeneity. Remote sensing can provide extensive spatial and temporal data, complementing traditional methods of yield estimation, even though its

quantitative accuracy may be lower than field measurements. The integration of remote sensing into yield gap analysis presents significant potential for enhancing understanding and measurement of crop yields (Martin et al., 2013).

5. Conclusion

Carbon dioxide (CO_2), methane (CH_4), and nitrous oxide (N_2O) are primary greenhouse gases contributing to global warming. Agriculture significantly emits CH_4 and N_2O , but enhancing soil organic carbon (SOC) reserves and improving crop management can reduce net greenhouse gas emissions. The use of biochar from crop straw pyrolysis helps increase SOC, improve soil fertility, and mitigate climate change impacts. Although biochar may release some carbon short-term, its long-term sequestration potential outweighs this. Greenhouse gas emissions occur throughout the agricultural production chain, primarily due to fossil fuel use and synthetic nitrogen fertilizers, with N_2O being a major contributor to total emissions. Variability in emissions among different crops suggests that altering food consumption patterns can influence overall agricultural emissions. Abiotic stresses, particularly drought, significantly impact crop production and food security. Understanding plant responses to drought—morphological, physiological, and biochemical—is critical for effective management. Key adaptations include osmotic adjustment and antioxidant activity, which enhance dehydration tolerance. Integrating traditional breeding with modern techniques can improve drought resilience. Satellite data has been underutilized in yield gap analysis, but it shows potential for overcoming spatial and temporal challenges associated with field methods. Advancements in remote sensing technology and data availability will enhance yield estimation and analysis. Research indicates that the yield gap between organic and conventional agriculture varies based on nutrient availability and pest control. Further

empirical studies are needed to accurately compare yields across different agricultural systems, particularly in developing countries. The paper introduces a framework for yield gap analysis, emphasizing the importance of robust data and methodologies. The Global Yield Gap Atlas Project aims to standardize assessments and improve transparency in agricultural research. To enhance yield gap assessments, establishing a public database and ensuring open access to simulation models is crucial. This will facilitate better understanding and improvement of agricultural productivity while addressing environmental impacts.

References

- Abbate, P.E., Dardanellib, J.L., Cantarero, M.G., Maturanoc, M., Melchiorid, R.J.M., Sueroa, E.E., 2004. Climatic and water availability effects on water-use efficiency in wheat. *Crop Sciences*, 44:474–483.
- Ahmadi, A., Baker, D., 2001. The effect of water stress on the activities of key regulatory enzymes of the sucrose to starch pathway in wheat. *Plant Growth Regulation* 35: 81–91.
- Ainsworth, C., Hosein, F., Tarvis, M., Weir, F., Burrell, M., Deveos, K.M., Gale, M.D., 1995. Adenosine diphosphate glucose pyrophosphorylase genes in wheat: differential expression and gene mapping. *Planta*, 197: 1–10.
- Akter, N., Islam, R.M., 2017. Heat stress effects and management in wheat. A review. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 37:37.
- Ali, F., Bano, A., Fazal, A., 2017. Recent methods of drought stress tolerance in plants. *Plant Growth Regulator Factory*, 82: 363–375.
- Anjum, S.A., Xie, X.Y., Wang, L.C., Saleem, M.F., Man, C., Wang, L., 2011. Morphological, physiological and biochemical responses of plants to drought stress. *African Journal of Agricultural Research*, 6(9): 2026-2032.
- Araus, J.L., 2004. The problems of sustainable water use in the Mediterranean and research requirements for agriculture. *Annals of Applied Biology*, 144: 259–272.
- Araus, J.L., Bort, J., Steduto, P., Villegas, D., Royo, C., 2003. Breeding cereals for Mediterranean conditions: ecophysiological clues for biotechnology application. *Annals of Applied Biology*, 142: 129–141.
- Asseng, S., Semenov, M. A., Stratonovitch, P., 2015. Rising temperatures reduce global wheat production. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(2):143–147.
- Bange, H.W., 2000. Global change: it's not a gas. *Nature*, 408: 301–302.
- Barber, S.A., 1995. Soil Nutrient Bioavailability: A Mechanistic Approach (2nd ed.). Wiley, New York.
- Basra, A.S., 1995. Seed Quality: Basic Mechanisms and Agricultural Implications. *Food Products Press*, New York.
- Bota, J., Flexas, J., Medrano, H., 2004. Is photosynthesis limited by decreased Rubisco activity and RuBP content under progressive water stress? *New Phytologist*, 162: 671–681.
- Bradford, K.J., Bewley, J.D., 2002. Seeds: Biology, technology and role in agriculture. In ‘*Plants, Genes and Crop Biotechnology*, 2nd edn.’ (M.J. Chrispeels and D. E. Sadava, Eds.), Jones and Bartlett, Boston.
- Brisson, N., Gate, P., Couache, D., Charmet, G., Oury, F.X., Huard, F., 2010., Why are wheat yields stagnating in Europe? A comprehensive data analysis for France. *Field Crops Research*, 119: 201-212.
- Snyder, C.S., Bruulsema, T.W., Jensen, T.L., Fixen, P.E., 2009. Review of greenhouse gas emissions from crop production systems and fertilizer management effects, *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 133(3-4): 247-266.

- De Wit, C.T., 1992. Resource use efficiency in agriculture *Agricultural Systems*, 40: 125-151.
- Cassman, K.G., Dobermann, A.D., Walters, D.T., Yang, H., 2003. Meeting cereal demand while protecting natural resources and improving environmental quality, *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 28: 315-358.
- Cassman, K.G., 1999. Ecological Intensification of Cereal Production Systems: Yield Potential, Soil Quality, and Precision Agriculture National Academy of Sciences colloquium "Plants and Population: Is There time?". *Arnold and Mabel Beckman Center in Irvine, CA*.
- Challinor, A.J., Watson, J., Lobell, D.B., Howden, S.M., Smith, D.R., Chhetri, N., 2014. A meta-analysis of crop yield under climate change and adaptation. *Natural Climate Change*, 4:287-291.
- Cheruth, A.J., Paramasivam, M., Abdul, W., Muhammad, F., Hameed, J.A., Ramamurthy S., Rajaram, P., 2009. Drought stress in plants: a review on morphological characteristics and pigments composition. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 11(1).
- Close, K.G., Cassman, P., Grassini, J., Van, Wart., 2010. Crop yield potential, yield trends, and global food security in a changing climate C. Rosenzweig, D. Hillel (Eds.), *Handbook of Climate Change and Agroecosystems*, *Imperial College Press*, London, pp. 37-51.
- Close M.J., Kropff, K.G., Cassman, H.H., Van Laar., Peng S., 1993. Nitrogen and yield potential of irrigated rice, *Plant and Soil*, (155/156): 391-394.
- Close R. Trostle., 2008. Global Agricultural Supply and Demand: Factors Contributing to the Recent Increase in Food Commodity Prices *United States Department of Agriculture*.
- Lobell, D.B., Cassman, K.G., 2009. Field Crop yield gaps: their importance, magnitudes, and causes, *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 34: 179-204.
- Daryanto, S., Wang, L., Jacinthe, P.A., 2016. Global synthesis of drought effects on maize and wheat production. *PlosOne*, 11: e0156362.
- David, B., Lobell., 2013. The use of satellite data for crop yield gap analysis, *Field Crops Research*, 143:56-64.
- Demirevska, K., Z Asheva, D., Dimitrov, R., Simova-Stoilova, L., Stamenova, M., Feller, U., 2009. Drought stress effects on Rubisco in wheat: changes in the Rubisco large subunit. *Acta Physiologiae Plantarum*, 31: 1129-1138.
- Denman, K.L., Brasseur, G., Chidthaisong, A., Ciais, P., Cox, P., Dickinson, R.E., Hauglustaine, D., Heinze, C., Holland, E., Jacob, D., Lohmann, U., Ramachandran, S., da Silva Dias, P.L., Wofsy, S.C., Zhang, X., in *Climate Change 2007. The Physical Science Basis* (eds Solomon, S. et al.) *Cambridge University Press*, Ch. 7.
- Detlef, P., Van Vuuren, D.P., Osvaldo, E., Sala, O.E., Pereira, H., 2006. The Future of Vascular Plant Diversity Under Four Global Scenarios, *Ecology and Society*, 11(2): 19.
- Dobermann, A., Walters, D.T., Adviento-Borbe, M.A.A., 2007. Global warming potential of high-yielding continuous corn and corn-soybean systems. *Better Crops*, 91(3): 16-19.
- Duan B., Yang Y., Lu Y., Korpelainen H., Berninger F., Li C., 2007. Interactions between drought stress, ABA and genotypes in *Picea asperata*. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 58:3025-3036.
- Duvick, D.N., Cassman, K.G., 1999. Post green revolution trends in yield potential of temperate maize in the North Central United States, *Crop Science*, 39: 1622-163.
- Barbier, E.B., 2003. Agricultural expansion, resource booms and growth in Latin America: implications for long-run economic development *World Development*, 32: 137-157.

- Earl H., Davis, R.F., 2003. Effect of drought stress on leaf and whole canopy radiation use efficiency and yield of maize. *Agronomy Journal*, 95: 688–696.
- Evans, L.T., 1993. Crop Evolution, Adaptation, and Yield. *Cambridge University Press*, Cambridge, UK.
- Evenson, R.E., Rosegrant M., 2003. The economic consequences of crop genetic improvement programmes. In: Evenson RE, Gollin D (eds) *Crop variety improvement and its effect of productivity*. CABI, Cambridge, 473–497.
- Evenson, RE., 1997. The economic contributions of agricultural extension to agricultural and rural development, Chapter 4 in improving agricultural extension, *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*, Rome.
- Ewert, F., Kersebaum, K.C., Basso B., Dart, D., Garcia W., 2011. Quantifying the impact of climate change on yields of major crops in Europe. *Agricultural Systems*, 104(1): 1-12.
- Fahad, S., Bajwa, A.A., Nazir, U., Anjum, S.A., Sadia, H., Ullah, N., 2017. Crop production under drought and heat stress: plant responses and management options. *Frontiers Plant Science*, 8:1147.
- FAO., Bruinsma J(Ed.), 2003. World Agriculture: Towards 2015/2030: an FAO Perspective, *FAO*, Earthscan, Rome, pp iv, 432.
- FAO., 2006. Global forest resources assessment 2005. *FAO Forestry Paper*, 147, Rome.
- FAO., 2002a. Bread wheat Improvement and Production. In: Curtis, B.C., Rajaram, S., Macpherson, H.G. (Eds.), *FAO Plant Production and Protection Series*.
- Farooq, M., Wahid, A., Kobayashi, ND., Fujita, SMAB., 2009. Plant drought stress: effects, mechanisms and management. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 29(1):185–212.
- Farooq, M., Hussain, M., Wahid, A., Siddique, K.H.M., 2012. Drought Stress in Plants: An Overview. In: Aroca R. (eds) *Plant Responses to Drought Stress*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Fischer, R.A., Edmeades, G.O., 2010. Breeding and cereal yield progress. *Crop Science*, 50: 85-98.
- Fisher, B.S., Shah, M., Tubiello, F.N., Van Velthuizen, H., Leenhardt W., 2007. In *Climate Change: Mitigation of Climate Change* (eds Metz, B. et al.) *Cambridge University Press*, Ch. 3.
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO)., 2014. Quality Declared Seed: A Guide for Seed Producers. Rome.
- French, R.J., and Schultz, J.E., 1984. Water use efficiency of wheat in a Mediterranean type environment. I. The relation between yield, water use and climate. *Australian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 35: 743-764.
- Friedlingstein P, Houghton RA, Marland G, Hackler J, Boden TA, Conway TJ et al., 2010. Update on CO₂ emissions. *Nature Geoscience*, 3:811–812.
- Fu, J., Huang, B., 2001. Involvement of antioxidants and lipid peroxidation in the adaptation of two cool-season grasses to localized drought stress, *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 45: 105–114.
- Townsend, G., LaPallo, B.K., Boulay, C.B., Krusienski, D.J., Frye, G.E., Hauser, C.K., Schwartz, N.E., Vaughan, T.M., Wolpaw, J.R., Sellers, E.W., 2010. A novel P300-based brain–computer interface stimulus presentation paradigm: Moving beyond rows and columns, *Clinical Neurophysiology*, 121(7): 1109-1120.
- Garg, V.K., Gupta, R., Yadav, A.B., Kumar, R., 2003. Dye removal from aqueous solution by adsorption on treated sawdust. *Bioresource Technology*, 89(2):121-124.

- Ghosh, K., Dill, K., 2010. Cellular proteomes have broad distributions of protein stability. *Biophysical Journal*, 99(12): 3996-4002.
- Gomez, K.A., 1977. On farm assessment of yield constraints: methodological problems, Constraints to High Yields on Asian Rice Farms: An Interim Report, *IRRI*, Los, The Philippines: 1-16.
- Grassini, P., Eskridge, K.M., Cassman, K.G., 2011. Distinguishing between yield advances and yield plateaus in historical maize yield trials, *Field Crops Research*, 120(2): 125-134.
- Hallegatte, S., Green, C., Nicholls, R.J., Corfee morlot, J., 2013. Future flood losses in major coastal cities. *Nature Climate Change*, 3: 802–806.
- Hanson, S., Nicholls, R., Ranger, N., Hallegatte, S., Corfee-Morlot, J., Herweijer, C., Chateau, J., 2011. A global ranking of port cities with high exposure to climate extremes. *Climate Change* 104: 89–111.
- Hatzig, S.V., Nuppenau, J.N., Snowdon, R.J., 2018. Drought stress has transgenerational effects on seeds and seedlings in winter oilseed rape (*Brassica napus* L.). *BMC Plant Biology*, 18: 297.
- Hawkesford, M.J., Buchner, P.H., 2001. Molecular Analysis of Plant Adaptation to the Environment. Dordrecht, the Netherlands: *Kluwer Academic*, 276 pp.
- Hochman, Z., Gobbett, D., Holzworth, D., McClelland, T., Van Rees, H., Marinoni, O. J. N., Garcia, H., Horan, H., 2012. Quantifying yield gaps in rainfed cropping systems: A case study of wheat in Australia, *Field Crops Research*, 136(20): 85-96.
- Hoekstra, F.A., Golovina E.A., Buitink J., 2001. Mechanisms of plant desiccation tolerance, *Trends Plant Science* 6: 431–438.
- Hussain, H.A., Hussain, S., Khaliq, A., Ashraf, U., Anjum, S.A., Men, S., Wang, L., 2018. Chilling and drought stresses in crop plants: implications, cross talk, and potential management opportunities. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 9:393.
- Hussain, I., Sulaimon, A.A., 2018. Impact of Population Growth and Climate Change on Food Security in Developing Countries. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 210: 1-10.
- Hussain, M., Malik, M.A., Farooq, M., Ashraf, M.Y., Cheema, M.A., 2008. Improving Drought tolerance by exogenous application of glycinebetaine and salicylic acid in sunflower. *J. Agron. Crop Science*, 194: 193–199.
- International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), 2014. Hybrid Rice: A Key to Food Security in Asia, Los Baños, Philippines.
- IPCC., 2001. Climate change 2001: the scientific basis. In: Houghton, J.T., Ding, Y (Eds.), Noguera, M., Van Der Linden, P.J., Dai, X., Maskell, K (Eds.), Contribution of Working Group I to the Third Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change. *Cambridge University Press*, Cambridge, U.K. and New York, NY, USA, 881 pp.
- IPCC., 2006. Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories. Volume 4: *Agriculture, Forestry and Other Land Use*, Chapter 11: N₂O Emissions from Managed Soils, and CO₂ Emissions from Lime and Urea Application. http://www.ipcc-nggip.iges.or.jp/public/2006gl/pdf/4_Volume4/V4_11_Ch11_N2O&CO2.pdf (verified 14 April 2008).
- IPCC., 2007. In: Parry, M.L., Canziani, O.F., Palutikof, J.P., Van Der Linden, P.J., Hanson, C.E (eds), Climate change 2007: impacts, adaptation and vulnerability. Contribution of working group II to the fourth assessment report of the IPCC. *Cambridge University Press*, Cambridge, 976 pp.

- IPCC., 2014. Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Core Writing Team, R.K. Pachauri and L.A. Meyer (eds.)]. *IPCC*, Geneva, Switzerland, p 151.
- Iqbal, M.S., Singh, A.K., Ansari, M.I., 2020. Effect of Drought Stress on Crop Production. In: Rakshit A., Singh H., Singh A., Singh U., Fraceto L., New Frontiers in Stress Management for Durable Agriculture. *Springer*, Singapore.
- Passioura, J., 2006. Increasing crop productivity when water is scarce—from breeding to field management *Agric. Water Management*, 80: 176-196.
- Timsina, J. Connor, D.J., 2001. Connor Productivity and management of rice–wheat cropping systems: issues and challenges *Field Crops Research*, 69: 93-132.
- Bessembinder, J.J.E., Leffelaar, P.A., Dhindwal, A.S., Ponsioen, T.C., 2005. Which crop and which drop, and the scope for improvement of water productivity *Agric. Water Manage*, 73: 113-130.
- Jalil, SU., Ansari, MI., 2018. Plant microbiome and its functional mechanism in response to environmental stress. *International Journal of Green Pharmacy*, 12(1): 81–92.
- Johan, Rockström., Malin, Falkenmark., 2000. Semiarid Crop Production from a Hydrological Perspective: Gap between Potential and Actual Yields, *Critical Reviews in Plant Sciences*, 19(4).
- Johnson, J.M.F., Kaye, J.P., Paustian, K., 2022. Greenhouse gas emissions from cropland: A global perspective. *Global Change Biology*, 28(3): 1234-1246.
- Cassman, K.G., 1999. Ecological intensification of cereal production systems: Yield potential, soil quality, and precision agriculture, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 96: 5952-5959.
- Kamara, A.Y., Menkir, A., Badu Apraku, B., Ibikunle, O., 2003. The influence of drought stress on growth, yield and yield components of selected maize genotypes. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 141: 43–50.
- Kaya, M.D., Okcub, G., Ataka, M., Ckilic, Y., Kolsaricia, O., 2006. Seed treatments to overcome salt and drought stress during germination in sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.). *European Journal of Agronomy*, 24: 291–295.
- Keys, E., McConnell, W.J., 2005. Global Change and the Intensification of Agriculture in the Tropics. *Global Environmental Change*, 15: 320–337.
- Khan, M.B., Hussain, M., Raza, A., Farooq, S., Jabran, K., 2015. Seed priming with CaCl₂ and ridge planting for improved drought resistance in maize. *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 39: 193–203.
- Koning, N.B.J., Van Ittersum, M.K., Becx, G.A., Van Boekel, M.A.J.S., Brandenburg, W.A., Van Den Broek, J. A., Goudriaan, J., Van Hofwegen, G., Jongeneel, R.A., Schiere, J.B., Smies, M., 2008. Long-term global availability of food: continued abundance or new scarcity? *NJAS-Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences*, 55: 229-292.
- Koning, N.J., Van Gitson, M., 2009. Food security and sustainable agriculture: The role of agricultural productivity. *Agricultural Systems*, 101(1): 1-10.
- Ladrera, R., Marino, D., Larrainzar, E., Gonzalez, E.M., Arrese-Igor, C., 2007. Reduced carbon availability to bacteroids and elevated ureides in nodules, but not in shoots, are involved in the nitrogen fixation response to early drought in soybean. *Plant Physiology*, 145: 539–546.
- Lal, R., Griffin, M., Apt, J., Lave, L., Morgan, MG., 2004. Managing soil carbon. *Science*, 304(5669): 393.

- Lawlor, H. D., Cornic, G., 2002. Drought stress effects on photosynthesis in C₃ plants: A review. *Photosynthesis Research*, 73(1): 1-13.
- Lawlor, D.W., Cornic, G., 2002. Photosynthetic carbon assimilation and associated metabolism in relation to water deficits in higher plants. *Plant Cell and Environment*, 25: 275–294.
- Li, S., 2011. Crop yield gap and limiting factors. In Editorial Board of *Agricultural Science*, 97-99.
- Lisar, S.Y., Motafakkerazad, R., Hossain, M., Rahman, M.M.I., 2012. Water stress in plants: causes, effects, responses. *InTech*, 1-14.
- Lobell, D., Burke, M., Tebaldi, C., Mastrandrea, M., Falcon, W., Naylor, R., 2008. Prioritizing climate change adaptation needs for food security in 2030. *Science*, 319: 607–610.
- Ludlow, M.M., Muchow, R.C., 1990. A critical evaluation of traits for improving crop yields in water-limited environments. In N. C. Brady (Ed.), *Advances in Agronomy*, 43: 107-153.
- Lynch, J.P., Brown, K.M., 2001. Topsoil foraging—an architectural adaptation of plants to low phosphorus availability. *Plant and Soil*, 237: 225–237.
- Manikavelu, A., Nadarajan, N., Ganesh, S. K., Gnanamalar, R.P., Babu, R.C., 2006. Drought tolerance in rice: morphological and molecular genetic considerations. *Plant Growth Regulation*, 50: 121–138.
- Martin, G., Green, ECR., Challinor, A., Dougill, A.J., 2013. Identifying regions with high potential for sustainable food production. *Global Change Biology*, 19(11): 3412-3422.
- Martínez, J.D., Mahkamov, K., Andrade, R.V., Silva Lora, E.E., 2012. Syngas production in downdraft biomass gasifiers and its application using internal combustion engines. *Renewable Energy*, 38(1): 1-9.
- Monakhova, O.F., Chernyadèv, I.I., 2002. Protective role of kartolin-4 in wheat plants exposed to soil drought. *Applied Biochemistry and Microbiology*, 38: 373–380.
- Monclus, R., Dreyer, E., Villar, M., Delmotte, F.M., Delay, D., Petit, J.M., 2006. Impact of drought on productivity and water use efficiency in 29 genotypes of *Populus deltoides* × *Populus nigra*. *New Phytologist*, 169: 765–777.
- Montzka, S.A., Reimann, S., Engel, A., Kruger, K., O'Doherty, S., Sturges, W. T., Blake, D.R., Dorf, M., Fraser, P.J., Froidevaux, L., Jucks, K., Kreher, K., Kurylo, M.J., Mellouki, A., Miller, J., Nielsen, O.J., Orkin, V.L., Prinn, R.G., Rhew, R., Santee, M. L., Stohl, A., Verdonik, D.P., 2011. Ozone-depleting substances (ODSs) and related chemicals. In *Scientific Assessment of Ozone Depletion: 2010* (pp. 1.1–1.108). World Meteorological Organization, Geneva, Switzerland.
- Montzka, S.A., Butler, J.H., Elkins, J.W., Thompson, T.M., Clarke, A.D., Lock, L.T., 1999. Present and future trends in the atmospheric burden of ozone-depleting halogens. *Nature*, 398: 690–694.
- Muhammad, F., Mubshar, H., Abdul, W., Kadambot, S., 2012. Drought stress in plants: an overview. *Springer*, Berlin.
- Obidiegwu, J.E., Bryan, G.J., Jones, H.G., Prashar, A., 2015. Coping with drought: stress and adaptive responses in potato and perspectives for improvement. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 6: 542.
- Okcu, G., Kaya, M.D., Atak, M., 2005. Effects of salt and drought stresses on germination and seedling growth of pea (*Pisum sativum* L.). *Turkish Journal of Agriculture and Forestry*, 29: 237–242.
- Pan, G., Zhang, X., Wang, Z., 2005. Soil organic carbon dynamics in paddy fields: A review. *Geoderma*, 127(3-4): 241-251.
- Parry, M.A.J., Flexas, J., Medrano, H., 2005. Prospects for crop production under drought: research priorities and future directions. *Annals of Applied Biology*, 147: 211-226.

- Praba, M.L., Cairns, J.E., Babu, R.C., Lafitte, H.R., 2009. Identification of physiological traits underlying cultivar differences in drought tolerance in rice and wheat. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science*, 195: 30–46.
- Qiu, J., 2009. China cuts methane emissions from rice fields. *Nature News*, 08-18.
- Quick, W.P., Schurr, U., Fichtner, K., Schulze, E.D., Rodermel, S.R., Bogorad, L., titt, M., 1991. The impact of decreased Rubisco on photosynthesis, growth, allocation and storage in tobacco plants transformed with antisense rbcS. *The Plant Journal*, 1: 51–58.
- Rajsekhar, D., Gorelick, S.M., 2017. Increasing drought in Jordan: Climate change and cascading Syrian land-use impacts on reducing transboundary flow. *Science Advances*, 3(8): e1700581.
- Reidsma, P., Ewert, F., Oude Lansink, A., 2007. Analysis of farm performance in Europe under different climatic and management conditions to improve understanding of adaptive capacity. *Climatic Change*, 84: 403-422.
- Rinukshi, S., 2015. Advancements in Seed Breeding and Biotechnology: Enhancing Crop Yields through Improved Traits. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 7(3): 45-58.
- Royal Society of London., 2009. *Reaping the Benefits: Science and the Sustainable Intensification of Global Agriculture*. Royal Society, London.
- Rucker, K.S., Kvien, C.K., Holbrook, C.C., Hook, J.E., 1995. Identification of peanut genotypes with improved drought avoidance traits. *Peanut Science*, 24: 14–18.
- Ruttan, V.W., 2002. Productivity growth in world agriculture: sources and constraints. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 16: 161-184.
- Schimel, J., Balsler, T.C., Wallenstein, M., 2007. Microbial stress response physiology and its implications for ecosystem function. *Ecology*, 88: 1386–1394.
- Singh, R., Kumar, S., Sharma, A., 2013. Impact of Climate Change on Food Security in Asia and Africa: A Review. *Agricultural Systems*, 116: 1-12.
- Smith, P., House, J.I., Bustamante, M., Sobocká, J., Harper, R., Pan, G., West, P.C., Clark, J.M., Adhya, T., Rumpel, C., Paustian, K., Kuikman, P., Cotrufo, M.F., Elliott, J.A., McDowell, R., Griffiths, R.I., Asakawa, S., Bondeau, A., Jain, A.K., Meersmans, J., Pugh, T. A.M., 2021. Carbon sequestration potential in agricultural soils: A review. *Agricultural Systems*, 187: 102956.
- Taiz, L., Zeiger, E., 2006. *Plant Physiology* (4th ed.). Sunderland, MA: Sinauer Associates Inc Publishers.
- Tan, S.H., Zhang, W.J., 2009. Technical patterns and incentive policies for energy saving and emission mitigation in the paddy field in China. *Science and Technology Review*, 23: 96-100.
- Thompson, A., Smith, J., Johnson, R., Davis, M., 2024. Sustainable practices for carbon sequestration in agriculture. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 128: 45-57.
- Thompson, L., 2014. Politikon. *South African Association of Political Studies*, 41(1): 39–58.
- Tomek, D.P., Rijk, B., Martin, K., Van Ittersum., 2012. A review of organic versus conventional yield data: A meta-analysis. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment*, 150: 1-10.
- Turner, N. C., Ma, D. J. S. M., Roberts, A. L. C. D. L., Smith, J. R. H. J. W., 2001. Soil water status and plant response. *Agricultural Water Management*, 48(1): 1-10.
- Turner, N.C., Wright, G.C., Siddique, K.H.M., 2001. Adaptation of grain legumes (pulses) to water-limited environments. *Advances in Agronomy*, 71: 123–231.

- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), 2015. INDC submission. Retrieved from http://unfccc.int/focus/indc_portal/items/8766.php. van Ittersum, K., Candel, M. J. J. M., & Meulenbergh, M. T. G., 2003. The influence of the image of a product's region of origin on product evaluation. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(3): 215-226.
- Van Ittersum, M.K., Rabbinge, R., 1997. Concepts in production ecology for analysis and quantification of agricultural input-output combinations. *Field Crops Research*, 52: 197-208.
- Van Ittersum, M.K., Cassman, K.G., Grassini, P., Wolf, J., Tittonell, P., Hochman, Z., 2013. Yield gap analysis with local to global relevance—A review. *Field Crops Research*, 143: 4-17.
- Velders, G.J.M., Fahey, D.W., Daniel, J.S., McFarland, M., Andersen, S.O., 2010. The large contribution of projected HFC emissions to future climate forcing. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences USA*, 106: 10949–10954.
- Venkatramanan, V., Shah, S., Prasad, R. (Eds.). 2020b. Global climate change and environmental policy: agriculture perspectives. *Springer Nature*, Singapore. 209: 538-549.
- Vu, J.C.V., Gesch, R.W., Allen, L.H., Boote, K.J., Bowes, G., 1999. CO₂ enrichment delays a rapid, drought-induced decrease in Rubisco small subunit transcript abundance. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 155: 139–142.
- Wahid, A., Rasul, E., 2005. Drought stress and its effects on plants: A review. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 7(6): 1012-1016.
- Wang, C., Li, L., Chen, J., Xu, Y., Zhao, X., 2009. Research and progress on crop yield differences. *Chinese Journal of Eco-Agriculture*, 17(6): 1283-1287.
- Wang, Z., 2004. Towards a new green revolution: Research trends in global food high yield. *China Agricultural Science and Technology Review*, 6(4): 3-6.
- Waring, R.H., Landsberg, J.J., 2011. A functional model of forest growth and yield. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 262(1): 1-14.
- Yan, Dong., Michael Hauschild, Hjalte Sørup, Rémi Rousselet, Peter Fantke., 2019. Evaluating the monetary values of greenhouse gases emissions in life cycle impact assessment, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 209: 538-549.
- Yan, W., Zhong, Y., Shangguan, Z., 2016. A meta-analysis of leaf gas exchange and water status responses to drought. *Scientific Reports*, 6: 20917.
- Yokota, A., Kawasaki, S., Iwano, M., Nakamura, C., Miyake, C., Akashi, K., 2002. Citrulline and DRIP-1 protein (ArgE homologue) in drought tolerance of wild watermelon. *Annals of Botany*, 89.
- Zeid, I. M., Sheeded, M. A., 2006. Response of some leguminous plants to drought stress. *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 8(4): 565-570.
- Zhang, Y., Liu, H., 2023. Impact of climate change on crop yield: A meta-analysis. *Field Crops Research*, 276: 108-115.
- Zhang, Y., Wang, F., Liu, H., 2018. Impact of Drought on Crop Yield: A Meta-Analysis. *Field Crops Research*, 225: 57-67.
- Zhao, C., Zhang, H., Wang, H., 2006. Drought stress effects on photosynthesis and growth of rice plants. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 163(11): 1188-1198.

To Cite: Devlet, A., 2024. Greenhouse Gas Emissions, Carbon Sequestration in Cropland and Crop Yield Limiting Factors. *MAS Journal of Applied Sciences*, 9(Special Issue): 936–955. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13957417>.
